

Examining the Attitude of Library and Information Science (LIS) Students in University of Calabar (Unical) towards Entrepreneurship

Ntui, Aniebiet Inyang

Department of Library and Information Science, Faculty of Education, University of Calabar

Abstract

The study was designed to investigate the attitude of LIS students towards entrepreneurship. Fifty-four students were sampled in connection with entrepreneurial attitude (inclinations, feelings, competence, intentions and desirability) of business start-up. The questionnaire was used to measure students' attitude based on their opinion and response about their entrepreneurial behaviour. Simple percentage method was adopted for the analysis of the study. Findings revealed that library and information science students are enterprising and have positive attitude towards entrepreneurship; 40% of students have the intention to become entrepreneurs; 58% of students possess entrepreneurial competence and 37% of students have desirability positive feelings about entrepreneurship. This shows that Library and Information Science students in university of Calabar possess positive attitude towards entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Attitude, Entrepreneurship, Library and information science Students, University of Calabar.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fostering entrepreneurship among students has become an important topic in Nigerian universities for generating economic growth and moving towards the entrepreneurial society, it is imperative because millions of graduates are released into the labour market on yearly basis from Nigerian tertiary institutions without adequate and corresponding job opportunities to match this turn out, in order to handle this situation that has given rise to so many societal problems, the Nigerian University Commission introduced entrepreneurial education into tertiary institution in order to equip them with entrepreneurial competence. Number of studies show that interest in entrepreneurship among students is growing. (Brenner (1991); Fleming (1994); Kolvereid (1996). Issa (1998).

Entrepreneurship education has been introduced in the curriculum of courses offered in the University of Calabar by Library and Information Science students. Entrepreneurship refers to the practice of identifying a social problem and using entrepreneurial principles like innovation to create and implement a venture that achieves change. Entrepreneurial librarianship offers specific techniques for creating an entrepreneurial environment in library and information service. Entrepreneurship is closely aligned with librarianship because of its mission and outcome. Today's librarians are innovators who explore new technologies in relentless pursuit of excellence. However, much can not be achieved except the attitude of students towards entrepreneurship is positive. Attitudes are inclinations, intentions, feelings, notions, fears about any specific topic. Some students may perceive entrepreneurship negatively while others may attach positive attributes to it. It has become necessary to find out the attitude of LIS students in UNICAL towards entrepreneurship.

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Entrepreneurship has been identified as a vital force for the process of economic development. Attitudes play a key role in fostering a successful entrepreneur. Empirical evidence shows that university students lack the appropriate attitudes towards entrepreneurship. The Nigerian government has employed various strategies in order to curb the problem of unemployment among university graduates. One of such strategies was the introduction of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institution to emancipate self-employment. Despite the various intervention by the government and National University Commission (NUC) to introduce entrepreneurial education in higher institutions in order to reverse the trend of unemployment and its associated vices, University graduates still remain unemployed and the number of unemployed graduates increases on a high rate. This measure has not achieved its full aim because of the attitude of students towards entrepreneurship. Librarians possess high potential in terms of starting their own business venture due to their education and exposure to entrepreneurial training as embedded in their discipline.

Possessing the right attitude goes a long way in establishing a successful Library and Information Science entrepreneur. It is a challenge that individuals outside the librarian profession are maximizing entrepreneurial opportunities in the field of librarianship and reaping its benefits while some trained librarians remain unengaged in any gainful activity. The right attitude towards entrepreneurship can reverse this situation and position librarians in a profitable entrepreneurial venture where they can harness the entrepreneurial opportunities in their field. However, in spite of these, it does appear that entrepreneurial intentions of students is

not clear as they graduate and leave school. It therefore becomes imperative to take a closer look at those attitudes, which have an effect on entrepreneurial plans of the graduands. Not much is known about the attitudes of attitude of library and information science students in university of calabar towards entrepreneurship

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to investigate the attitude of library and information science students toward entrepreneurship development. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Determine the intention of library and information science students towards entrepreneurship.
- ii. Examine competence and skills needed for successful entrepreneurship.
- iii. Examine the efforts of library and information science students toward self employment and job creation in library and information field.
- iv. Examine the feelings of students towards information marketing.
- v. Determine if entrepreneurship education stimulates entrepreneurial success among students

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Survey research was adopted for the study. Survey research is considered most suitable because it reveals facts about students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship. The study was conducted in the University of Calabar in Cross River State. The study population comprised of final year undergraduate students of library and information science, University of Calabar for the 2012/2013 academic session. The total population of the study was 61. Out of 61 students, 54 students were sampled for the study. The instrument used for the collection of data was the questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed by the researchers. The validity and reliability of the instrument were properly ascertained by three educational research experts.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Entrepreneurial Intention of LIS Students

Table 1: I intend to start a business of my own.

Option	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
SA	22	40.5
A	18	28
SD	6	12.5
D	8	19
TOTAL	54	100

Source: Research Field Survey, 2014

The table above indicated that 40.5% of the respondents strongly agreed (SA) to start businesses of their own their own, 28% started agreed (A) 12.5% stated strongly disagreed indicating that they do not have such intention while 19% indicated that they do not have the intention.

4.2 Entrepreneurial Competence of LIS Students

Table 2: Engaging in entrepreneurship makes me feel a sense of competence.

Option	Number of Respondent	Percentage %
SA	30	58
A	19	34
SD	5	8
D	-	-
TOTAL	54	100

Source: Research Field Survey, 2014

The table above presents that 58% of the respondents strongly agreed (SA) that engaging in entrepreneurship males them feel a sense of competence, 34% started agreed while 8% of the respondents strongly disagreed that engaging in entrepreneurship does makes them feel a sense of competence.

Table 3: Engaging in entrepreneurship need a lot of effort.

Option	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
SA	32	55
A	18	33
SD	2	6
D	2	6
TOTAL	54	100

Source: Research Field Survey, 2014

The table above presents the percentage of respondents who stated that engaging in entrepreneurship need a lot of effort. 55% were strongly agreed that entrepreneurship need a lot of effort, 33% stated agreed, while 6% stated strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively.

Table 4: Entrepreneurship education provides adequate knowledge for entrepreneur.

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SA	20	87
A	32	55
SD	1	4
D	1	4
TOTAL	54	100

Source: Research Field Survey, 2014.

The table above shows that 37% of the respondents strongly agreed that entrepreneurship education provides adequate knowledge for entrepreneur. 55% stated agree that entrepreneurship education provide adequate knowledge for entrepreneur while 4% strongly disagree and disagree respectively.

Table 5: Entrepreneurship education is a positive force that drives entrepreneurship.

Option	No. of respondents	Percentage %
SA	21	38
A	26	50
SD	3	4
D	4	8
Total	54	100

Source: Research Field Survey, 2014

The table above presents that entrepreneurship education is a positive force that drives entrepreneurship. According to the respondents, 38% indicated strongly agreed, 50% agree, 4% strongly disagreed and disagreed.

Table 6: Information Literacy

Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SA	20	36
A	27	52
SD	4	8
D	3	4
Total	54	100

Source: Research Field Survey, 2014

The table 4.6 above shows the percentage of the respondents on information literacy. 36% of the respondents indicated strongly agree, 52% stated agree, 8% shows strongly disagree and 4% stated disagree. It therefore means that information literacy is very important skill needed for successful entrepreneurship.

Presentation of Data on Bar and Pie Graph

Bar graph represented the options of the respondents and their percentage in tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Fig. 1: Multiple bar graph showing the number of respondents and percentage based on the key provided

The bar graph showed that 40.5%, 58% and 55% indicated strongly agree, 28%, 34% and 33% stated agree. This shows that there is significant relationship between library and information science and entrepreneurship.

Bar chart represented the options of the respondents and their percentage in tables 4, 5 and 6.

Fig. 2: Multiple bar graph showing the number of respondents and percentage analyzed in tables 4, 5 and 6

The bar graph presents that entrepreneurship education and information literacy set space for adequate knowledge and efficiency in entrepreneurial operation.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship attitude plays a very important role, therefore it should be encourage among students in order to build an entrepreneurial society. Entrepreneurship education in the curriculum of Tertiary Institution should be enhanced with positive attitude of students towards it. This research work draws a conclusion in order to achieve a sustainable and effective entrepreneurship and to reverse negative attitude towards entrepreneurship and to encourage competence and skills, entrepreneurial intention and desire among Library and Information Science Students.

The researcher concludes that entrepreneurship attitude is very important and necessary as it aid the effective and efficient economic growth and development in the nation. It also provides opportunities for Library and Information Science students to be engage in the profitable venture.

Recommendations

Based on the results of findings, the researcher recommends the following that:

- Government policies should be made to combine entrepreneurship education with positive attitude in order to get good results from entrepreneurship education.
- Seminars should be organized for training and retraining of Librarians and LIS Graduate in order to see the need of possessing positive attitude towards entrepreneurship.
- Advanced research should be carried out in order to produce more findings on entrepreneur attitude of students of Library and Information Science.
- Finally, student of Library and Information Science should endeavour to work towards a more positive attitude towards entrepreneurship in order to be successful in the field of entrepreneurship.
- The curriculum should be restructured and major improvements should be made, like exposing students to carry out entrepreneurial projects in order to inculcate entrepreneurial skills, competence and attitude in them.
- Government should give aid to students that desire to start up business.

REFERENCES

Ajzen, I. (1987). Attitude traits and actions: Dispositional prediction of behaviour in personality and social

- psychology. In L. Berkowitz (ed.). *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 20. 1-63. New York: Academic Press.
- Brenner, O. C., Pringle, C. D. and Greenhus, J. H. (1991). Perceived fulfilment of organisational employment versus Entrepreneurship: Work, Values and carrier intentions of business College graduates. *Journal and Small Business Management*, 29, (4). 62-74
- Fleming, P. (1994). The role of structured intervention in shaping graduates entrepreneurship. *Irish Business and Administrative Research*, 15, 146-147
- Issa, A. O (1998) information Dissemination to the rural person in Nigeria: A librarians perspective paper presented at 3rd Nigeria Association of education for national Development (NAED) at federal college of Education. P.1
- Kolvereid, L. (1996). Prediction of Employment States Choice and intention. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 20(3). 45 & 57
- Venesaar, U., Kolbre, E. and Piliste, T. (2005). Student attitude towards entrepreneurship at Tallinn University of Technology 10(154).

The IISTE is a pioneer in the Open-Access hosting service and academic event management. The aim of the firm is Accelerating Global Knowledge Sharing.

More information about the firm can be found on the homepage:

<http://www.iiste.org>

CALL FOR JOURNAL PAPERS

There are more than 30 peer-reviewed academic journals hosted under the hosting platform.

Prospective authors of journals can find the submission instruction on the following page: <http://www.iiste.org/journals/> All the journals articles are available online to the readers all over the world without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. Paper version of the journals is also available upon request of readers and authors.

MORE RESOURCES

Book publication information: <http://www.iiste.org/book/>

Academic conference: <http://www.iiste.org/conference/upcoming-conferences-call-for-paper/>

IISTE Knowledge Sharing Partners

EBSCO, Index Copernicus, Ulrich's Periodicals Directory, JournalTOCS, PKP Open Archives Harvester, Bielefeld Academic Search Engine, Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek EZB, Open J-Gate, OCLC WorldCat, Universe Digital Library , NewJour, Google Scholar

